

Thermodynamic and multi-step kinetic analysis of slow pyrolysis of natural rubber-silanised cellulose composites with 30–55 phr filler content

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ABSTRACT

Pyrolysis is a promising thermochemical process for waste reduction and energy recovery. Natural rubber (NR) composites filled with 30, 45, and 55 phr silanised cellulose (CELS) were prepared and characterised by SEM and FTIR techniques. Thermogravimetric curves for heating rates of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 20 °C·min⁻¹ were measured in an inert gas. Kinetic parameters were determined by isoconversional kinetic analysis using the Friedman model-free method and a model-based method. By applying the generalised master plot method, it was found that the pyrolysis process follows an autocatalytic mechanism involving two kinetically independent, parallel pathways, each pathway consisting of two sequential steps. The results show that silanisation of cellulose has a positive effect on composite thermal stability, but only up to a specific content of CELS. At high loadings, the resulting silica-rich ash can act as a solid acid catalyst, accelerating secondary cracking reactions during pyrolysis.

Innovative approaches for determining the formal thermodynamic parameters have been presented. The first method is based on the Eyring equation and the knowledge of $E_{\alpha} = f(\alpha)$ and $A_{\alpha} = f(\alpha)$ from the model-free method, providing the thermodynamic parameters as a function of the entire conversion range, α . The second method is based on the results of model-based kinetic analysis. The method makes it possible to determine these parameters for individual steps of a multi-step model and, thus, to compare the energy demand, spontaneity, and change in disorder of the system in the transition state for these steps.

1. Introduction

The global production of NR in 2024 reached approximately 15 million tonnes, with the majority consumed in tyre manufacturing and industrial goods [1]. Within composite applications, fossil-based fillers such as carbon black and silica remain dominant due to their reinforcing properties, accounting for more than 90 % of NR composite formulations [2]. Biodegradable fillers – including cellulose, lignin, and natural fibres – represent a small but growing segment [3,4]. This growth is driven by sustainability initiatives and the development of bio-based materials for automotive, footwear, and consumer products [5]. The growing global rubber production [1,6] results in a large amount of waste, which must be addressed with the least possible environmental impact and in accordance with the rules of the circular economy.

The energetic utilisation of NR-based waste involves recovering its inherent chemical energy through thermal processes such as direct

combustion (incineration), gasification, and pyrolysis. These methods convert end-of-life rubber products into heat, power, and secondary fuels, contributing to waste management and reducing dependence on fossil fuels [7,8]. Among these methods, pyrolysis stands out as a promising thermochemical technique for both waste reduction and energy recovery. Pyrolysis converts waste rubber into oil, gas, and char, which can be used as alternative fuels or raw materials for new chemicals [9–11].

As the production of biodegradable rubber composites increases, the number of end-of-life products will also increase, which will need to be processed in pyrolysis reactors under conditions different from those of composites with fossil-based fillers. A kinetic and thermodynamic analysis of the pyrolytic decomposition of biodegradable rubber composites is critical for the design and optimisation of such reactors.

Kinetic analysis provides essential formal parameters such as activation energy E_a , pre-exponential factor A , and reaction model, usually

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derived from models based on Arrhenius theory and/or advanced isoconversional methods [12]. A fundamental technique for investigating the kinetic mechanism in thermally controlled processes is thermogravimetric (TG) analysis. The pyrolysis decomposition process of NR proceeds by a radical mechanism through depolymerisation, condensation, and degradation reactions to form isoprene, dipentene, and other compounds [13]. The kinetic description of the thermal decomposition of rubber is often presented in the form of two consecutive steps using Friedman or power-law models [14] or the truncated Sestak-Berggren function [15]. The basic mechanism of cellulose pyrolysis follows the Broido-Shafizadeh scheme [16,17], which includes the decomposition of cellulose into active cellulose, which subsequently decomposes into volatiles, light gases, and char. In [18,19], the authors modify this scheme by including two parallel pathways of cellulose decomposition into active cellulose and dehydrocellulose [18], or char and water [19]. Active cellulose is subsequently decomposed by two parallel pathways into levoglucosan and volatile compounds, or char. For characterising the kinetics of the thermal degradation of cellulose, an isoconversional approach with model-free methods [20] is often chosen, or power-law models [21,22] or the random chain scission model [18,19,23] are used.

Basically, there are two approaches to studying the kinetics of polymer pyrolysis. The first aims to describe thermal decomposition based on the actual chemical pathways involved. This methodology constructs models from elementary reaction steps, such as chain scission, side-group elimination, radical formation, and subsequent propagation. Each reaction is represented by its own rate law and kinetic parameters, providing physically meaningful insights into the decomposition process. While this approach offers superior predictive capability and a deeper understanding of reaction chemistry, it requires extensive experimental data—often combining TG, DSC, evolved gas analysis (TG-FTIR, TG-MS, TG-GC-MS), and spectroscopic techniques—to identify intermediates and validate reaction schemes [24,25]. Advanced modelling methods are also often used [26–28].

From an engineering perspective, a practical, and robust method for rapidly determining the kinetic data necessary for predicting and optimising pyrolysis processes is required. Thus, another approach to studying the kinetics of polymer pyrolysis is a formal kinetic description involving dominant kinetic steps, which may include several overlapping chemical and/or physical sub-processes. The formal kinetic description is usually based on TG analysis performed under non-isothermal conditions, followed by the implementation of isoconversion single-step model-free methods or, in more advanced cases, by using multi-step modelling. To determine the predominant reaction mechanism for individual steps, the master-plot method is applied. This approach can be found, e.g., in [12,15,29,30], and is also used in this study.

Thermodynamic evaluation includes calculations of formal thermodynamic parameters, such as Gibbs energy, enthalpy, and entropy, and offers insights into the feasibility and spontaneity of the process, as well as the energy requirements for chemical and physical transformations during pyrolysis. The standard approach for calculating thermodynamic parameters is the method presented by Kim et al. [31], which requires knowledge of the activation energy values from isoconversional methods, the pre-exponential factor obtained from the Kissinger method [32], and the peak temperature corresponding to the highest mass loss rate in the DTG curve. This approach is often used to determine formal thermodynamic parameters for biomass thermal decomposition [33,34] or co-pyrolysis of plastics and biomass [35,36].

There is a lack of work devoted to a detailed kinetic and thermodynamic analysis of the thermal degradation of composites based on NR and surface-modified lignocellulosic fibres. Previous studies have mainly focused on composites with unmodified fibres and investigated their extraction and bonding with NR, including mechanical reinforcement, interfacial adhesion, and dispersion [37–40], as well as the mechanical, chemical, and physical properties of these composites [41–43]. A recent study by the authors [44] was devoted to the kinetic analysis of

the pyrolysis of NR composites containing unmodified cellulose fibres (NR-CEL). This new study aims to fill the research gap and provide new insights and original results from the kinetic and thermodynamic analysis of the pyrolytic degradation of NR composites filled with silanization-modified cellulose fibres (NR-CELS). For this purpose, NR-CELS composites with a graded filler content (30, 45, and 55 phr CELS, where phr means parts per hundred rubber) were prepared, and TG/DTG analyses were performed at six heating rates. SEM and FTIR techniques were used to characterise the structure of the samples. First, the Friedman isoconversion model-free method was applied to evaluate the effect of conversion and filler content on the apparent activation energy. Second, a multi-step kinetic analysis was performed; the kinetic triplet (E_a , A, and the model parameters) was determined for the individual steps, and the effect of filler content was studied. The master-plot method was applied to identify the kinetic degradation mechanism of the individual steps. Third, formal thermodynamic parameters were determined using the results from both the model-free method and the multi-step model, and the effect of filler content was evaluated.

The main novelty of this study lies in the overall concept of the kinetic and thermodynamic analysis of the pyrolysis degradation of NR-CELS composites from an engineering perspective. Within this concept, an innovative approach to determine the formal activation thermodynamic parameters was introduced, which makes it possible to obtain these parameters as a function of the entire conversion range from the model-free method results. Another innovative approach is to determine the formal thermodynamic parameters for the individual steps of the multi-step model. Finally, the study provides original results of the kinetic and thermodynamic analysis of the NR-CELS composites pyrolysis. That is, NR composites with surface-modified cellulose, which has never been published before, to the best of the authors' knowledge.

The authors believe that this concept can serve as a theoretical basis for the kinetic and thermodynamic analysis of pyrolysis processing, not only of rubber composites at the end of their life. It may also ultimately contribute to improving the energy efficiency of the pyrolysis process.

2. Materials and methods

The SMR 10 natural rubber was sourced from Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. Cellulose fibres surface-modified with silane coupling agents (CELS), containing 99 % cellulose, bulk density 90–110 g/cm³, were supplied from Greencel, Ltd. Hencovce, Slovakia. Three types of composites were prepared: with the CELS content 30 phr (NR-CELS 30 sample), 45 phr (NR-CELS 45 sample), and 55 phr (NR-CELS 55 sample) according to the procedure described in the authors' recent work [44]. Only for comparison purposes, selected results for unmodified cellulose (CEL), vulcanised NR without cellulose (NR-CEL 0), and unmodified cellulose composite NR-CEL 55 published in [44] were used in some parts of this study.

The micromorphology of the prepared NR-CELS composites was studied on their fracture surfaces using SEM analysis under the same conditions as described in [44].

The FTIR spectra were obtained via the ATR (Attenuated Total Reflectance) method. The specimens were laid and pressed on the single-reflection diamond ATR crystal with a pressure device. The FTIR spectra were collected using an FT-IR spectrometer Nicolet iS50 (ThermoScientific, USA) equipped with a DTGS detector on Smart Orbit ATR accessory. An FT-IR spectrometer Nicolet iS50 (ThermoScientific, USA) equipped with a DTGS detector on Smart Orbit ATR accessory was used for the FTIR spectra collection. The measurement conditions included a spectral region 4000–400 cm⁻¹, spectral resolution 4 cm⁻¹; 64 scans; Happ-Genzel apodisation.

Thermogravimetric analysis was performed using the Setaram Setsys 18TM device with simultaneous TG/DTA analysis. The weight of the samples was about 10.5 mg. Corundum crucibles were used, and the experiment was conducted in an inert Ar (6 N) atmosphere. Each sample was analysed at six heating rates: 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 20 °C/min, over a

temperature range of 20–600 °C. For each analysis, the TG/DTA curve of a blank sample was subtracted from the TG/DTA curve of the sample to reduce the noise of the experimental data. A blank TG/DTA run was always conducted under conditions identical to those of the subsequent sample measurement.

3. Theoretical background of kinetic and thermodynamic analysis

3.1. Kinetic analysis

In general, the rate of the thermal degradation process of the condensed phase can be expressed as

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where k is the rate constant dependent on the temperature T and $f(\alpha)$ is the reaction model of the extent of conversion α . The degree of conversion α is expressed in this work as follows:

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{m_i - m(t)}{m_i - m_f} \quad (2)$$

where m_i is the initial mass of the sample, m_f is the mass of the final residue after the experiment, and $m(t)$ is the mass at a given moment of time t .

If the rate constant k varies with temperature according to the Arrhenius equation in the form

$$k(T) = A \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

and a constant heating rate β ($\beta = dT/dt$) is used in thermal analysis, then Eq. (1) takes the form:

$$\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT} = A \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (4)$$

where A (in s^{-1}) and E_a (in $J \cdot mol^{-1}$) are the pre-exponential factor and the activation energy, respectively, and $R = 8.314 J \cdot K^{-1} \cdot mol^{-1}$ is the universal gas constant.

Equation (4) represents the basis of isoconversional differential kinetic methods. The isoconversional approach specifies that “the reaction rate at constant extent of conversion is only a function of temperature” [12].

Friedman's method [45], a widely employed model-free differential method, is utilised in this work:

$$\ln\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)_{\alpha,i} = \ln[f(\alpha)A_{\alpha,i}] - \frac{E_a}{RT_{\alpha,i}} \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (5), i indicates an individual heating rate. The value of E_a can be derived from the Friedman plot, i.e. from the slope of $\ln(d\alpha/dt)_{\alpha,i}$ against $1/T_{\alpha,i}$ for each value α . Model-free methods make it possible to obtain additional knowledge about the decomposition mechanism from the analysis of the variation of E_a with conversion.

Another approach to the kinetic analysis of the decomposition process is the model-based method, in which the reaction model $f(\alpha)$ in Eq. (1) takes a specific form (n^{th} -order, autocatalytic, power law, dimensional diffusion, Avrami-Erofeev, etc.). This approach is mostly used in multi-step processes; the output is the so-called kinetic triple (i.e., the values of the activation energy, pre-exponential factor, and parameters of the model) for each step. An overview of the most used kinetic models can be found, e.g., in [12,46]. In this work, the empirical Šesták-Berggren (SB) model was used in a modified form of the extended Prout-Tompkins model [12]:

$$f(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n \alpha^m \quad (6)$$

where $(1 - \alpha)$ represents the relative proportion of reactant, and α corresponds to the relative proportion of product. The parameters n and m are the orders of reaction and autocatalysis, respectively. The parameter values are determined by fitting the SB equation to experimental data [47]. The main advantage of the SB model lies in its empirical flexibility: the exponents m and n can be adjusted to account for the combined effects of molecular chain scission, crosslinking breakdown, and the catalysis of volatile products inherent in polymer pyrolysis. Essentially, all kinetic models based on physical-geometric or physical-chemical assumptions (order-based models, diffusion models, phase-boundary reactions, nucleation, and nuclei growth, etc.) can be expressed through the SB model using non-integral values of their kinetic exponents [15,30]. However, the parameters m and n lack a mechanistic interpretation; therefore, a complementary analysis, such as master plots, is necessary to confirm the model fitting results [48,49].

3.2. Thermodynamic analysis

Thermodynamic characteristics, such as enthalpy, entropy, and Gibbs energy, can be determined from the kinetic parameters (E_a , A) based on the formal thermodynamic expression of the transition-state theory:

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = E_a - RT \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = E_a + RT \ln\left(\frac{k_B T}{hA}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger - \Delta G^\ddagger}{T} \quad (9)$$

where $k_B = 1.381 \cdot 10^{-23} J \cdot K^{-1}$ is the Boltzmann's constant and $h = 6.626 \cdot 10^{-34} J \cdot s$ is the Planck constant. The derivation of equations (7) to (9) is given in [Supplementary material](#).

The equations for the calculation of the activation thermodynamic parameters ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger (Eqs. (7) to (9)) are often used for the analysis of the pyrolysis of biomass and plastics [31,50–52]. In these applications, the parameter A is calculated according to the Kissinger method [32,53]:

$$A = \frac{\beta E_a}{RT_p^2} \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{RT_p}\right) \quad (10)$$

A common approach involves determining the parameter A using Eq. (10), as its value is determined directly from the value of the activation energy E_a calculated for the corresponding heating rate β . On the other hand, this method has certain limitations; its derivation assumes that A is constant, E_a is constant, and the reaction follows first-order kinetics [53].

However, solid-phase decomposition processes, in general, condensed-phase reactions, do not occur at a constant activation energy. The isoconversional approach to the kinetic analysis of decomposition processes makes it possible to obtain the activation energy, which varies with the conversion α :

$$E_a = E_a(\alpha) = E_a \quad (11)$$

Similarly, the pre-exponential factor A is a function of α :

$$A = A(\alpha) = A_\alpha \quad (12)$$

The A_α dependence can be determined from the assumption of mutual correlation between kinetic parameters, i.e. from the so-called kinetic compensation effect:

$$\ln A_\alpha = aE_a + b \quad (13)$$

where a and b are the compensation parameters; for more details, see, e.

g. [54–56].

Substituting Eqs. (11) and (12) into Eqs. (7) to (9) yields the following:

$$\Delta H_{\alpha}^{\ddagger} = E_{\alpha} - RT_p \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta G_{\alpha}^{\ddagger} = E_{\alpha} + RT_p \ln \left(\frac{k_B T_p}{h A_{\alpha}} \right) \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta S_{\alpha}^{\ddagger} = \frac{\Delta H_{\alpha}^{\ddagger} - \Delta G_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}}{T_p} \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta G_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ is the effective activation Gibbs energy, $\Delta H_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ is the effective activation enthalpy, and $\Delta S_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ is the effective activation entropy, and all three parameters are a function of conversion α . Eqs. (14) to (16) represent an innovative approach to determining thermodynamic parameters.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Interfaces/morphologies of NR-CELS composites

The adhesion, distribution, and compatibility between the filler and the matrix were studied on NR-CELS composites by SEM. The fracture surfaces of the analysed samples were observed. Observations were performed on unfilled vulcanised rubber (NR–CEL 0 sample) and NR–CELS 30 and NR–CELS 55 composites. To accurately characterise the filler particles incorporated into the composites, CELS was also examined by SEM, and representative micrographs are shown in Fig. 1. As can be observed, CELS particles exhibit a fibrous morphology with a rough and flaky surface, in sharp contrast to unmodified cellulose (Fig. 1 in [44]), which displays a smooth texture. The CELS particle agglomerates measured in the SEM images reached thicknesses ranging from 2.70 to 6.94 μm and widths between 12.89 and 21.53 μm . In comparison, the SEM analysis of unmodified cellulose (CEL) revealed significantly larger agglomerates, with thicknesses ranging from 2.70 to 6.37 μm and widths of 19.24 to 28.33 μm [44]. These results clearly indicate that silanisation reduces the extent of particle aggregation, leading to finer and better-dispersed cellulose particles. Furthermore, the increased surface roughness observed after silanisation is expected to improve the interfacial compatibility with the natural rubber matrix by providing a greater effective surface area and additional anchoring sites for filler–matrix interactions. Thus, silanisation not only facilitated the preparation of smaller cellulose agglomerates but also contributed to the enhancement of the adhesion potential in the subsequent composite system.

Figs. 2 and 3 present SEM micrographs of the NR-CELS composites, showing both the fracture surfaces (Fig. 2a, 3a) and the cross-sections (Fig. 2b, 3b). In the cross-sectional views of both composites, a

relatively small number of cavities (black spots) can be observed. This number is lower compared to composites filled with unmodified cellulose (see Fig. 2 in [44]). The reduction in cavities may be attributed to the surface roughening of the cellulose fibres during silanisation, which decreases their absorbency and facilitates the cross-linking of silane derivatives with the rubber matrix.

Overall, the SEM images indicate good filler incorporation into the NR matrix, confirming the positive effect of cellulose treatment with silane derivatives. The silane groups on the surface of the modified cellulose can form chemical bonds with the functional groups of the rubber, which improves interfacial adhesion at the molecular level. Furthermore, surface modification increases the surface energy of the cellulose, thus enhancing its interaction with the polymer matrix. This effect contributes not only to improved adhesion but also to a more homogeneous dispersion of the filler. A uniform distribution of the cellulose leads to more effective contact between the filler and the matrix, which is critical for stress transfer and overall composite performance. The positive influence of silanisation on filler dispersion and interfacial bonding observed in this study is consistent with findings reported in previous works [57–60]. When comparing Figs. 2 and 3 of this study with Fig. 2 in [44], the beneficial effect of silanisation on both the morphology and adhesion of the cellulose-rubber composites becomes evident.

4.2. FTIR analysis

FTIR analysis was conducted on NR, CEL, CELS, and composites NR-CEL 55 and NR-CELS 55.

The FTIR spectrum of NR in the first part of the spectral region (Fig. 4a) shows a broad band at 3285 cm^{-1} attributed to O–H stretching vibrations, which indicates some oxidation processes in NR. Further bands at 3031, 2959, 2919, 2852 and 2726 cm^{-1} are attributed to C–H stretching vibrations of –C=C– in 1,4-unit, asymmetric and symmetric C–H stretching vibrations of CH_3 unit, symmetric C–H stretching vibrations of CH_2 unit, followed by sympathetic vibration, respectively [61]. In the spectra of CEL and CELS, the bands at 3332 cm^{-1} belong to O–H stretching vibrations. The bands at 2893, 2896 cm^{-1} belong to C–H stretching vibrations of methylene groups [62]. The intensity of these bands, mainly the band at 3332 cm^{-1} belonging to O–H vibrations, is lower for the silanised cellulose (CELS) than for the pure one (CEL). Chemical modification (silanisation) consumes free –OH groups in cellulose and builds inorganic siloxane linkages on its surface [63].

Adding unmodified cellulose, CEL, to NR significantly impacts O–H stretching vibration in the composite NR-CEL 55, which is broad and shifted to 3346 cm^{-1} . This phenomenon may be caused by the formation of a zinc-cellulose complex in the composite [64]. ZnO and other cross-linking agents employed to prepare the vulcanised NR create active sites for cross-linking in the NR backbone. During the preparation of the NR–CEL composite, they favour the disruption of hydrogen bonds in

Fig. 1. SEM images of CELS (BSE).

Fig. 2. SEM images of NR-CELS 30, a) fracture surface, b) section.

Fig. 3. SEM images of NR-CELS 55, a) fracture surface, b) section.

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of NR, CEL, NR-CEL55, CELS and NR-CELS 55 samples in regions a) 4000–2500 cm⁻¹ and b) 1800–400 cm⁻¹.

cellulose, allowing them to participate in the cross-linked network. The OH groups in the chemical structure of the cellulose form a complex with zinc. Other bands in the NR–CEL 55 spectrum are at almost the same positions as in the case of NR. However, adding modified cellulose, CELS, to NR has only a small effect on the O–H stretching vibration, shifting to 3296 cm^{-1} in the NR–CELS 55 composite. Chemical treatment of cellulose with a silane coupling agent before compounding results in the consumption of surface hydroxyl groups through silane hydrolysis and condensation, i.e., the silane layer effectively blocks native hydroxyl sites [65].

In the second part of spectral region (Fig. 4b) main bands at 1661 , 1446 , 1375 , 1310 , 1127 , 1037 , and 838 cm^{-1} can be observed in the NR spectrum which belong to C=C stretching vibration of 1,4-unit, CH_2 deformation vibration, scissoring vibration of CH_3 in *cis*-1,4-, 3,4-, and 1,2-units, scissoring vibration of CH_3 or CH in *cis*-1,4-unit, stretching vibration of C–C main chain in *cis*-1,4-unit, stretching or wagging vibration of $\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{C}$ in *cis*-1,4-unit and out-of-plane bending vibration of C–H in the $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ group of *cis*-1,4-unit, respectively [61]. The *cis*-1,4-configuration of polyisoprene was confirmed.

The band at 1640 cm^{-1} corresponds to the vibration of water molecules absorbed on cellulose (CEL, CELS). Minor shifts in the water-bending band may be observed as a result of altered moisture interactions. The main bands at 1428 , 1366 , 1315 , 1160 , 1027 and 896 cm^{-1} belong to bending vibrations of CH_2 , CH_2 umbrella, CH, C–O–C asymmetric vibrations, –OH and C–O–C stretching at β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-glycosidic linkages in cellulose. Again, a significant difference in intensity is seen in the –OH band (1027 cm^{-1}) for CEL and CELS, confirming the successful silanisation.

The band at 1428 cm^{-1} correlates with the crystalline structure present in the cellulose, whereas the band at 896 cm^{-1} is linked to its amorphous region [62]. The specific band associated with the asymmetric valence vibration of Si–O–Si cellulose bridge (around 1040 cm^{-1}) in the silanised cellulose (CELS) is probably overlapped with the large and intense C–O–C vibration bands of cellulose in the same spectral region [66].

As already mentioned, the absorption peaks at 1428 cm^{-1} and 896 cm^{-1} are sensitive to the crystal structure of cellulose and can be used to calculate changes in the crystallinity. The ratio of absorbance at $\sim 1429\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (CH_2 bending, crystalline) to $\sim 898\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C–O–C stretch, amorphous) is known as the crystallinity index or lateral arrangement index (LOI) [67]. The total crystallinity index (TCI) is also used to evaluate qualitative changes in the cellulose crystallinity and is calculated as the ratio of the absorbance at $\sim 1372\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (CH_2 symmetric bend) to that at $\sim 2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C–H stretch, amorphous) [67]. The crystallinity indices were calculated from the peak-height ratios. For CEL, the values are LOI 0.55 and TCI 0.44, and for CELS, LOI 0.48 and TCI 0.36. The results show the effect of silanization on the decrease in the cellulose crystallinity.

The FTIR spectra of the samples NR, NR–CELS 55 and mainly of NR–CEL 55 show, besides typical bands for *cis*-1,4-polyisoprene (NR) and CEL or CELS, two extra bands around 1540 cm^{-1} and 1398 cm^{-1} , which belong to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of CO_2 originating from zinc stearate [68]. This compound was formed from stearic acid and ZnO vulcanising agents during NR vulcanisation. The intensity of the peaks indicates that the sample NR–CEL 55 contains the highest amount of this compound.

4.3. TG/DTG analysis

Fig. 5 shows the TG curves of the cellulose samples (CEL and CELS), natural rubber (NR and NR–CEL 0) and the samples NR–CELS 30, NR–CELS 45, and NR–CELS 55 measured at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, Fig. 6 shows the corresponding DTG curves. The behaviour of individual samples during thermal decomposition in inert gas can be compared from Figs. 5 and 6.

The principal zone of CEL pyrolysis occurs between temperatures of

Fig. 5. TG curves, heating rate $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Fig. 6. DTG curves, heating rate $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

$271\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $368\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with $T_{\text{peak}} = 348\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. For CELS, this zone is between $286\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $368\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with $T_{\text{peak}} = 347\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Thus, silanisation increased the thermal stability of cellulose from the point of onset degradation temperature, shifting it towards higher values, in accordance with [69,70], likely due to the formation of covalent Si–O–C and Si–O–Si structures, which are stronger than the native glycosidic C–O–C bonds [71–73].

On the other hand, cellulose silanisation increases the rate of degradation; it increases the peak height on the DTG curve (compare curves CEL and CELS, Fig. 6). In studies [37,74,75], an increase in the maximum degradation rate of silanised cellulose was also observed. The reason may be the reduction in the cellulose crystallinity after silanisation, as confirmed by our FTIR analyses and in [76,77]. Silanisation involves introducing silane groups onto the cellulose surface, which can disrupt hydrogen bonds between cellulose chains and thereby reduce the overall crystallinity of cellulose, making it more amorphous [78,79]. Also probably shortens cellulose chains by acid- or base-catalysed hydrolysis of β -(1 \rightarrow 4) glycosidic linkages during silanization [80,81]. These structural modifications make the material more susceptible to thermal scission.

The small weight loss visible on the TGA curves of CEL and CELS (Fig. 5) between temperatures of approximately 50 and $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ corresponds to the evaporation of water and other low molecular weight components. The pyrolysis residue at a temperature of $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is higher for silanised cellulose, 19.94% , while for pure cellulose it is 18.05% , which confirms the successful incorporation of silane groups onto the cellulose surface, leading to increased char formation [66,82].

The main decomposition interval of NR is between 310 and $470\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with $T_{\text{peak}} = 377\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a DTG peak of $17.7\text{ } \%/ \text{min}^{-1}$, see Figs. 5 and 6. Additionally, the characteristic shoulder for NR can be seen at elevated

temperatures on the DTG curve. Vulcanisation reduces the degree of polymerisation due to chain scission associated with sulphur cross-linking reactions [83,84]. This is manifested on the DTG curve of sample NR-CEL 0 (Fig. 6) by a slight movement of T_{peak} to lower temperatures, a slight reduction of the mass loss rate and a straightening of the shoulder compared to the DTG curve of NR. During the vulcanisation process, cross-linking reactions occur, forming a structure that also increases the stability of the char residues [85], which is evidenced by an increase in char yield compared to unvulcanised NR in Fig. 5.

Incorporating a filler, CELS, into NR decreases its thermal stability and shifts the main reaction zone of the composite to lower temperatures (compare the curves for NR and for NR-CELS composites in Figs. 5 and 6). As shown in Fig. 6 and in Figs. 8, 10, and 12, the DTG curves for the NR-CELS samples exhibit two peaks at approximately 360 °C and 380 °C. With increasing filler (CELS) content in the composite, the height of the first peak increases, while the height of the second peak decreases (compare DTG curves NR-CELS 30, NR-CELS 45, and NR-CELS 55). The filler content influences the degradation mechanism of the composite during pyrolysis.

Figs. 7 to 12 present TG and DTG curves measured at six different heating rates. As expected, increasing the heating rate shifts the main reaction zone (mass loss) to higher temperatures due to reduced heat-transfer efficiency. The peak temperatures for all heating rates of individual composites are given in Table S1.

4.4. Kinetic and thermodynamic analysis

Non-isothermal kinetic analysis was performed using NETZSCH Kinetics Neo software (v. 2.4.4.6) and thermogravimetric curves experimentally measured at six different heating rates (Figs. 7, 9, and 11).

4.4.1. Kinetic and thermodynamic analysis based on the model-free method

The Friedman method (Eq. (5)) has been used for kinetic modelling. Fig. S1 in the Supplementary material gives the temperature dependence of conversion α and Fig. S2 shows the course of simulated mass loss with respect to temperature, calculated according to the Friedman model. Fig. 13 illustrates the computed values of the apparent activation energy E_{α} depending on conversion α for all NR-CELS composites analysed. Fig. S3 shows the course of $\log A$ on conversion α calculated from the values of E_{α} according to the kinetic compensation effect (Eq. (13)). All these curves were calculated for $\alpha = 0.01-0.99$, with a step of 0.01. It is clear from Fig. 13 that the courses of the activation energy curves are roughly the same for all composites. Up to approximately a conversion value of 0.7, the curves exhibit an essentially increasing character; then, they decrease. The significant rise in the values of E_{α} for $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ could potentially be associated with reactions occurring in the residues. To avoid limit phenomena (the moisture release process for $\alpha < 0.1$ and the

Fig. 7. TG curves, composite NR-CELS 30.

Fig. 8. DTG curves, composite NR-CELS 30.

Fig. 9. TG curves, composite NR-CELS 45.

Fig. 10. DTG curves, composite NR-CELS 45.

reactions in the residues for $\alpha > 0.95$), the curves were further analysed in a range of $\alpha = 0.05-0.95$, as also recommended in [12].

Table 1 presents the E_{α} values calculated according to the Friedman method (Eq. (5)) for selected conversion values for all composites. The arithmetic averages and the corresponding standard deviations are added, as well as the maximum values of E_{α} , all these values are calculated from the entire data set for $\alpha = 0.05$ to 0.95, with a step of 0.01. The determined values of E_{α} are within the range of values reported, e.g., in [15,19,23,86-88] for the pyrolysis of natural rubber and/or cellulose.

Fig. 11. TG curves, composite NR-CELS 55.

Fig. 12. DTG curves, composite NR-CELS 55.

Fig. 13. The variation of apparent E_a with conversion α according to the Friedman method.

From the results in Fig. 13 and Table 1, the influence of filler content on the degradation behaviour of NR-CELS composites can be evaluated. From the comparison of the E_a values of the NR-CELS 30 and NR-CELS 45 samples in Fig. 13 and Table 1 shows, that the higher CELS content supports the thermal stability of the samples. The pyrolytic decomposition of the NR-CELS 45 composite is more energy-intensive than the degradation of the NR-CELS 30 composite for the entire conversion range α . However, a further increase in filler content (in our case, 55 phr CELS) does not support a further increase in thermal stability, as can be

Table 1

E_a values (in $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) calculated according to the Friedman method for selected degrees of conversion.

Conversion	NR-CELS 30	NR-CELS 45	NR-CELS 55
0.05	181.399	200.622	198.989
0.10	199.794	207.065	213.363
0.20	213.645	217.179	210.241
0.30	229.792	247.840	239.802
0.40	236.637	244.272	240.287
0.50	254.233	279.949	259.918
0.60	279.348	316.372	303.255
0.70	285.819	334.237	324.027
0.80	266.070	305.217	302.325
0.90	248.611	283.074	281.910
0.95	242.261	279.893	288.297
Average ^{*)}	245.316	270.175	263.385
STD ^{*)}	27.982	42.283	39.856
Maximum	286.505	334.986	324.183

^{*)} The arithmetic average of the E_a values and the corresponding standard deviations (STD), as well as the maximum values, were calculated from the entire data set for $\alpha = 0.05\text{--}0.95$ with a step of 0.01.

seen from the E_a curve in Fig. 13 and from the values in Table 1 for NR-CELS 45 and NR-CELS 55 composites. Thus, silanised cellulose enhances the thermal stability of NR-CELS composites, but only up to a specific content of filler (CELS).

This behaviour at high CELS loading can be explained as follows. At 55 phr, the NR matrix may become oversaturated with functional groups of the silanised cellulose, limiting effective matrix–filler interaction. Excessive filler content promotes filler–filler interactions and agglomeration [89], reducing rubber–filler adhesion and producing heterogeneous thermal conductivity [90], which can localise heat and initiate premature degradation, thereby lowering E_a . In addition, high CELS content facilitates the formation of thermally stable silicate structures, which transform into silica-rich ash and may catalyse secondary cracking reactions [91–93]. The increased ash content observed for the NR-CELS 55 composite (Fig. 5) supports this conclusion. Higher CELS content also results in a greater proportion of amorphous cellulose (Chapter 4.2), which degrades more readily, further contributing to reduced thermal stability at high filler loading.

Hence, the excessive content of silanised cellulose in the composite can lead to filler agglomeration, heterogeneous heat transfer, and an overabundance of active surface sites, all of which can accelerate catalytic decomposition.

The formal thermodynamic parameters ΔH_a^\ddagger , ΔG_a^\ddagger , and ΔS_a^\ddagger were calculated using Eqs. (14) to (16), (with T_p being the average value of T_p for all heating rates for individual composites, see Table S1) and the data from $E_a - \alpha$ and $\log A_a - \alpha$ curves shown in Figs. 13 and S3. The effective activation enthalpy values ΔH_a^\ddagger shown in Fig. 14 logically indicate the same trend as the apparent activation energy curves in Fig. 13. Their values are slightly lower than the E_a values, which follows from Eq. (14). Parameter ΔH_a^\ddagger indicates the amount of energy required to reach the products from the reactants. A higher value indicates that the reaction requires more energy to reach the products, making it slower. Conversely, a lower value suggests a faster reaction because less energy is needed. In terms of mechanism, a high ΔH_a^\ddagger suggests that the reaction involves breaking strong bonds or forming a highly unstable intermediate. The effective activation Gibbs energy ΔG_a^\ddagger gives a measure of the spontaneity of the reaction at the transition state. It represents the difference in Gibbs energy between the reactants and the transition state; it is usually positive because the transition state is at a higher energy level than that of the reactants. A lower value means that the transition state is more accessible, suggesting a more straightforward or less energy-intensive mechanism. The effective activation entropy ΔS_a^\ddagger reflects the change in disorder when moving from reactants to the transition state. A positive value indicates an increase in disorder, often associated with the formation of more complex or less ordered transition states. Conversely, a negative value suggests a more ordered transition state, which can

Fig. 14. The variation of $\Delta H_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ with conversion α (Eq. (14)).

imply a more organised or concerted mechanism.

The data in Figs. 14 and 16 show the most energy-intensive region for $\alpha \approx 0.6-0.8$ (Fig. 14), which also shows the least ordered system (Fig. 16). It is clear from $\Delta G_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ values in Fig. 15 that with increasing α , reaching the transition state becomes more demanding and therefore the mechanism of thermal decomposition of composites becomes more complex. Figs. 14–16 also show the effect of filler content on the change in thermodynamic parameters depending on the degree of conversion. The NR-CELS 45 and NR-CELS 55 composites show higher $\Delta G_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ values for $\alpha > 0.5$, which means higher thermal stability than the NR-CELS 30 composite for this α range, i.e., reaching the transition state is more difficult. The NR-CELS 45 composite exhibits higher $\Delta H_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta S_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ values in the conversion range of 0.3 to 0.9 compared to the NR-CELS 55 composite, which exhibits higher values of these parameters for $\alpha \rightarrow 1$. This could indicate that thermal degradation of the NR-CELS 55 composite produces more silica-like residues in this range, which can act as a solid acid catalyst and reduce the energy demand of the decomposition.

4.4.2. The multi-step kinetic and thermodynamic analysis

It is unlikely that the thermal decomposition of the NR-CELS samples occurs in a single step. The DTG curves in Figs. 8, 10, 12 and the dependence of E_{α} on α in Fig. 13 show that the pyrolysis degradation of the composites must be a multi-step process. For this reason, a multi-step kinetic analysis was performed using model-based isoconversional kinetic methods. A Prout-Tompkins model in the form of Eq. (6) was used for the multi-step kinetic modelling of the NR-CELS composites thermal decomposition. Multi-step kinetic analysis was performed in the Kinetics Neo software through a model-fitting procedure based on statistical evaluation criteria (the coefficient of determination (R^2), the residual sum of squares (RSS) and the F-test).

The formal final kinetic multi-step schema is represented in this form:

The schema comprises two kinetically independent parallel steps

Fig. 15. The variation of $\Delta G_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ with conversion α (Eq. (15)).

Fig. 16. The variation of $\Delta S_{\alpha}^{\ddagger}$ with conversion α (Eq. (16)).

(branches), each having two consecutive steps. Note that these steps do not represent individual reactions, and the scheme does not represent a simple linear series of reactions. It is a formal kinetic description; these steps are believed to represent the major features of the thermal decomposition process; however, they likely contain several overlapping chemical and/or physical sub-processes.

Kinetic analysis of NR-CELS samples using a multi-step model with kinetically independent processes is in accordance with [30], where the authors recommend this approach for “a mixture of different materials that react in partially overlapping temperature regions (typically coprecipitates and composites)”. Both main components of the composite (NR and cellulose) undergo thermal decomposition in overlapping stages [15,18,19]. It is also evident from our TG/DTG experiments that the active pyrolysis zones of NR and CELS overlap (see Fig. 5 or Fig. 6). Therefore, the choice of the presented kinetic multi-step model seems appropriate for systems exhibiting multi-step thermal degradation and partially overlapping decomposition peaks. The suitability of the model is also confirmed by fitting the model to the experimental data and the high values of R^2 coefficients in Fig. S4.

The apparent kinetic characteristics of the individual steps calculated according to the Prout-Tompkins model are given in Table 2. The E_a values in Table 2 fall within the ranges published for the thermal degradation of NR [14,15] and/or cellulose [19,23,87].

The results in Table 2 show that within the multi-step model, the first steps of both branches (steps A \rightarrow B, D \rightarrow E) have, on average, lower E_a values than the following steps B \rightarrow C and E \rightarrow F. Overall, the lowest E_a is for step A \rightarrow B. The values of the pre-exponential factor A show the same trends. To compare these results with the results of the Friedman model-free method (given in the previous Chapter 4.4.1), the average E_a values for all four steps of individual composites were calculated from Table 2 (in $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$): E_a (NR-CELS 30) = 254 ± 50 ; E_a (NR-CELS 45) = 274 ± 60 ; E_a (NR-CELS 55) = 274 ± 70 . The relatively large values of the standard deviations of the activation energies confirm the correctness of the use of the multi-step kinetic model [12]. The effect of CELS content on the average E_a values for individual NR-CELS composites shows the same trend as when using the Friedman model-free method: increasing CELS content increases the E_a value and thus the thermal stability, only up to a specific content. However, the multi-step model makes it possible to determine the energy demand of individual steps of the whole process. From the perspective of the mechanism of the individual steps, steps D \rightarrow E and E \rightarrow F appear to be more complicated, because the values of the parameter m , which represents the autocatalytic order, are an order of magnitude higher than for steps A \rightarrow B and B \rightarrow C.

To further clarify the kinetic mechanism of pyrolytic degradation of the NR-CELS samples, each step of the proposed model was evaluated against several theoretical models using the generalised master plot

Table 2

Computed values of E_a ($\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), $\log A$ ($\log\text{ s}^{-1}$) and the parameters n and m of the model $f(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n \alpha^m$ for the individual steps.

	Step A \rightarrow B			Step B \rightarrow C		
	NR-CELS 30	NR-CELS 45	NR-CELS 55	NR-CELS 30	NR-CELS 45	NR-CELS 55
E_a	167.547	171.102	168.655	290.437	312.188	359.114
$\log A$	12.058	12.491	12.425	20.058	21.815	26.896
n	2.175	2.136	2.242	2.382	2.665	3.938
m	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010
contribution	0.379	0.371	0.340	0.366	0.371	0.375
	Step D \rightarrow E			Step E \rightarrow F		
	NR-CELS 30	NR-CELS 45	NR-CELS 55	NR-CELS 30	NR-CELS 45	NR-CELS 55
E_a	277.697	294.563	264.905	281.684	316.605	304.611
$\log A$	21.304	22.771	20.479	20.600	23.510	20.690
n	1.859	1.473	1.675	0.857	0.994	1.443
m	0.578	0.465	0.525	0.154	0.167	0.206
contribution	0.129	0.132	0.164	0.126	0.126	0.121

method [48], as shown in Fig. 17.

The evaluation shows that steps $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow C$ correspond to an n^{th} -order reaction kinetic mechanism for all the composites analysed and the majority of the α . At values of α from about 0.7, it is sometimes difficult to determine whether the step proceeds according to an n^{th} -order mechanism or a diffusion mechanism. The values of the parameters n and m for these steps in Table 2 also correspond to an n^{th} -order reaction mechanism; the autocatalytic order m reaches values approaching zero. The influence of different CELS content in the composites is particularly evident in step $B \rightarrow C$: with increasing filler content, the reaction order n increases. The reaction orders are not integers, which means that the steps are not elementary processes but have a more complex mechanism. Step $B \rightarrow C$ for the NR–CELS 55 composite is likely to have a particularly complicated mechanism; the value of E_a is the highest of all steps of all composites, and the order of n reaches a value of almost 4. This may be attributed to the higher amount of modified cellulose present in this system, which can influence the microstructure and thermal behaviour of the composite through changes in filler–matrix interactions, rather than indicating a distinct chemical mechanism. This may cause the formation of thermally stable silicate structures during pyrolysis, which transform into silica-rich ash. At the same time, internal and external diffusion of pyrolysis products can occur in the polymer. Such diffusion-related effects are consistent with the general behaviour of filled elastomers during thermal degradation.

Steps $D \rightarrow E$ and $E \rightarrow F$ appear to correspond to the mechanism of the random scission model for all composites in the conversion range $\alpha < 0.5$. For conversion $\alpha > 0.5$, a specific model cannot be easily determined. For composites NR–CELS 30 and NR–CELS 45, step $E \rightarrow F$ clearly corresponds to the random scission model. Step $D \rightarrow E$ for all the composites analysed and step $E \rightarrow F$ for the composite NR–CELS 55 likely involve several overlapping models for $\alpha > 0.5$: the n^{th} -order model, diffusion and random scission model. The values of the parameters n and m for these steps ($D \rightarrow E$ and $E \rightarrow F$) in Table 2 correspond to an autocatalytic reaction mechanism, with the values of the autocatalytic parameter m being higher for step $D \rightarrow E$ than for step $E \rightarrow F$ for all composites. The influence of different CELS content in composites is particularly evident in step $E \rightarrow F$: with increasing filler content, the reaction orders n and m increase.

From the above, it follows that the proposed multi-step model consisting of two parallel processes can be described in the following way: the first parallel process (steps $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow C$) follows the mechanism of reactions of the n^{th} -order model, and the second parallel process (steps $D \rightarrow E$ and $E \rightarrow F$) follows the autocatalytic mechanism. This scheme of two parallel pathways, one of which is described by the n^{th} -order model and the other by the autocatalytic model, can generally be considered as an autocatalytic mechanism of the composite thermal decomposition [94,95]. Some products of the chemical reactions involved in steps $A \rightarrow B$ and/or $B \rightarrow C$ are assumed to enter as reactants in the reactions in steps $D \rightarrow E$ and/or $E \rightarrow F$. In addition, steps $D \rightarrow E$ and $E \rightarrow F$ could be autocatalysed by products from some of the reactions occurring in these steps. These interactions likely reflect the complex interplay between the degradation behaviours of NR and CELS under pyrolytic conditions [13,20,41]; however, the kinetic model captures these effects in an aggregated form and does not resolve them as individual mechanistic events. It can be assumed that diffusion processes of reacting substances also apply in this autocatalytic mechanism. Such transport-related limitations are plausible in filled polymer systems [86,96], although their individual contributions cannot be unambiguously separated from other overlapping phenomena within the kinetic framework.

The pyrolytic decomposition of an NR–CELS composite is governed by a complex interplay of thermal degradation mechanisms and catalytic influences introduced by the inorganic modification of the cellulose phase. Vulcanised NR decomposes primarily through random scission of polyisoprene chains by a radical mechanism, yielding a mixture of hydrocarbons, while silanised cellulose undergoes depolymerisation and

fragmentation, producing oxygenated volatiles and leaving behind silica-like residues. These residues, formed from the thermal degradation of organosilane groups, can act as solid acid catalysts, promote secondary cracking reactions, and enhance deoxygenation and dehydration pathways [97,98].

The formal thermodynamic characteristics ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were determined for the individual steps of all three composites according to Eqs. (7) to (9) using the data from Table 2 (with T being the average value of T_p for all heating rates for the individual composites, see Table S1) and are shown in Figs. 18–20. The activation enthalpy values ΔH^\ddagger in Fig. 18 have the same trend as the activation energy values E_a given in Table 2, which follows from Eq. (7). The most energy-intensive step appears to be step $B \rightarrow C$, in which the energy demand increases with increasing CELS content. On the other hand, the least energy-intensive step is step $A \rightarrow B$, for which the CELS content has no effect on ΔH^\ddagger . Steps $D \rightarrow E$ and $E \rightarrow F$ have the highest ΔH^\ddagger values for the NR–CELS 45 composite, which may indicate a relatively complex thermal decomposition mechanism that requires a higher amount of thermal energy. The complex mechanism of these steps for the NR–CELS 45 composite is also confirmed by the activation entropy values ΔS^\ddagger in Fig. 20; these steps show a relatively significant increase in disorder during the transition to the transition state. In general, step $B \rightarrow C$ of the NR–CELS 55 composite exhibits the highest disorder in the transition state. The processes that can increase ΔS^\ddagger during the pyrolysis of NR–CELS composites include radical chain scission of the polyisoprene backbone, depolymerisation of cellulose into volatile fragments, cleavage of sulphur cross-links releasing small sulphur-containing molecules, and the evolution of gaseous products such as hydrocarbons and CO_2 . Slightly negative ΔS^\ddagger values in step $A \rightarrow B$ indicate a transition state of higher order than the bulk composite, reflecting constrained, often cyclic, or cooperative rearrangements that precede bond cleavage [99–101]. The values of the activation Gibbs energy ΔG^\ddagger in Fig. 19 show that reaching the transition state is more demanding in step $B \rightarrow C$ for all composites and the most demanding in step $E \rightarrow F$ for the NR–CELS 55 composite. A high positive value of ΔG^\ddagger indicates that the reaction pathway is unfavourable thermodynamically and kinetically and requires significant energy input to proceed.

To determine the effect of the heating rate, the parameters ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger were calculated according to Eqs. (7) to (9) using the data from Table 2 and substituting the peak temperatures T_p from Table S1 for cooling rates of 2 °C/min and 20 °C/min. The heating rate in the measured range (2 °C/min to 20 °C/min) has a minimal effect on the determined values of the activation thermodynamic parameters (see Figs. S5–S7). A higher heating rate slightly reduces the values of ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger , which is probably related to the shorter time for heat and mass transfer.

5. Conclusion

Based on the presented comprehensive kinetic and thermodynamic study of NR–CELS composites pyrolysis, the following main conclusions can be formulated:

- Cellulose silanisation increases the thermal stability of cellulose from the onset temperature of the main degradation reaction zone and simultaneously increases the rate degradation.
- The thermal degradation mechanism of the NR–CELS composite during pyrolysis is manifested by two peaks on the DTG curve; the peak heights are influenced by the amount of filler (CELS).
- The average E_a values calculated from the data set for $\alpha = 0.05$ – 0.95 by the Friedman model-free method are as follows for the individual composites (in $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$): $E_a(\text{NR–CELS 30}) = 245 \pm 28$; $E_a(\text{NR–CELS 45}) = 270 \pm 42$; $E_a(\text{NR–CELS 55}) = 263 \pm 40$. The shape of the $E_a = f(\alpha)$ curves suggests a multi-step thermal degradation of the NR–CELS composites.

Fig. 17. Comparison of the model $f(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n \alpha^m$ for individual steps (parameters n and m given in Table 2) with some theoretical kinetic models. Theoretical models: F^{th} is the n^{th} order model; D3 is a 3D diffusion model (Jander model); R3 is the phase-boundary reaction model, contracting volume; A3 is the 3D Avrami-Erofeev nucleation and nuclei growth model; L2 is the random scission model.

Fig. 18. Calculated activation enthalpy ΔH^\ddagger of individual steps of the proposed multi-step kinetic model.

Fig. 19. Calculated activation Gibbs energy ΔG^\ddagger of individual steps of the proposed multi-step kinetic model.

Fig. 20. Calculated activation entropy ΔS^\ddagger of individual steps of the proposed multi-step kinetic model.

- Formal activation thermodynamic parameters ΔH^\ddagger_α , ΔG^\ddagger_α , and ΔS^\ddagger_α were calculated from the results of the Friedman model-free method using a novel approach that makes it possible to obtain the thermodynamic parameters as a function of the entire conversion range. The transition of reactants to products is most energy-intensive in the conversion range of approximately 0.6 to 0.8, where the disorder of

the system is also highest. Reaching the transition state appears to be most difficult at the final stage of the conversion.

- The silanisation of cellulose improves the thermal stability of NR-CELS composites, but only up to a specific content of filler. At high loadings (55 phr CELS in our case), silica-rich ash formed from silanised cellulose during pyrolysis can act as a solid acid catalyst, accelerating secondary cracking reactions during pyrolysis.
- A multi-step kinetic analysis was performed using the extended Prout-Tompkins model. The resulting multi-step decomposition scheme comprises two kinetically independent parallel branches, each with two consecutive steps: $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$; $D \rightarrow E \rightarrow F$. The calculated kinetic triplets of the individual steps for the three composites analysed are given in Table 2. The influence of different CELS content on the pyrolysis mechanism is particularly noticeable in steps $B \rightarrow C$ and $E \rightarrow F$.
- Using the master-plot method, it was found that the overall pyrolysis degradation of NR-CELS composites is controlled by an autocatalytic mechanism. The individual steps predominantly show the n^{th} order mechanism (steps $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow C$) or the random scission mechanism (steps $D \rightarrow E$ and $E \rightarrow F$); at higher conversions, the diffusion mechanism is also involved.
- The formal activation thermodynamic parameters ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , and ΔS^\ddagger were calculated for individual steps ($A \rightarrow B$, $B \rightarrow C$, $D \rightarrow E$, and $E \rightarrow F$) of the multi-step decomposition scheme using the results of multi-step kinetic analysis. This approach makes it possible to assess the energy demand of transformation processes, the disorder of the system, and the spontaneity of reaching the transition state at each step.

The presented article can serve as a guide to the kinetic analysis of the pyrolysis decomposition of polymers from an engineering perspective; it offers a practical, robust method for rapidly determining kinetic and thermodynamic data.

Future work would be desirable to focus on a more detailed mechanistic kinetic analysis down to the level of individual chemical reactions, including the investigation of structure–property relationships, especially the influence of silanisation on the molecular interactions within NR–CELS systems. However, further experimental research will be necessary, e.g., evolved gas analysis (TGA-GC-MS or Py-GC-MS), spectroscopic analyses (Raman, NMR), and surface and morphological analysis (TEM, XRD), all preferably in-situ. The involvement of computational modelling techniques (Molecular Dynamics, Reactive Force Field, Computational Fluid Dynamics, etc.) would also be appropriate. In a broader context, future work may focus on exploring different types and concentrations of silane coupling agents and extending the thermal analysis to include long-term ageing behaviour.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jana Dobrovská: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petra Skalková:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Elizaveta Iudina:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Sylva Holešová:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Monika Kawuloková:** Data curation. **Róbert Janík:** Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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Data availability

Data are available from the ZENODO Repository DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16939440

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